

Spatiotemporal congruency modulates weighting of visuotactile information in displacement judgments

Nedim Goktepe¹, Knut Drewing², and Alexander C. Schütz³

Abstract—Combining or integrating information from multiple senses often provides richer and more reliable estimates for the perception of objects and events. In daily life, sensory information from the same source often is in close spatiotemporal proximity. This can be an important determinant of whether and how multisensory signals are combined. The introduction of advanced technical display systems allows to present multisensory information in virtual environments. However, technical displays can lack the spatiotemporal fidelity of the real world due the rendering delays. Thus, any spatiotemporal incongruency could alter how information is combined. In the current study we tested this by investigating if and how spatially and temporally discrepant tactile displacement cues can supplement imprecise visual displacement cues. Participants performed a visual displacement task with visual and tactile displacement cues under spatial and temporal incongruency conditions. We modelled how participants combined visual and tactile information in visuotactile condition using their performance in visual only condition. We found that temporal incongruency lead to an increase in tactile weights although they were correlated with the congruency condition. In contrast, the spatial incongruency led to individual differences altering cue combination strategies. Our results illustrate the importance of spatiotemporal congruency for combining tactile and visual cues when making visual displacement judgments. Given the altered cue combination strategies and individual differences, we recommend developers to adopt individual spatiotemporal calibration procedures to improve the efficiency of the sensory augmentation.

Index Terms—Multisensory integration, Sensory substitution, Sensory augmentation, Vision, Haptics, Spatial Congruency, Temporal Congruency, Individual differences

I. INTRODUCTION

We are living in a multisensory environment. In everyday life, we often have access to object information from different modalities. The brain is tasked with combining sensory information from multiple modalities to build a coherent and unified percept that represents the world in a practical and useful manner. However, combining sensory information from distinct sensory systems poses a great challenge. Perhaps, the biggest part of this challenge is to figure out which sensory information belongs to

which object, known as the binding problem (review in [1]). The root of the binding problem is that the brain is constantly bombarded by sensory information gathered by different sensory channels that needs to be mapped in a way that only corresponding sensory information are grouped together to build a multisensory percept of an object. Therefore, with each incoming new sensory signal, the brain has to decide whether the new signal has a common cause with the previous signals for combining it with an existing object or treat it separately.

For establishing a causal relationship among signals, the brain resorts to various heuristics in its arsenal. One key heuristic is the spatiotemporal congruency of multisensory signals [2]. That is, how much two signal overlaps in time and space. For instance, imagine being in a conversation with two other people. There would be two groups of visual signals and two groups of auditory signals that needed to be matched. One way to correctly match these signals would be to analyze the spatial and temporal congruency of the signals. All the visual and auditory signals coming from one person would originate from the same location at the same time, which is different than the signals from the other person. Furthermore, information from different sensory channels are processed and capture attention based on their spatial and temporal relation to each other even when they are clearly distinct or task irrelevant ([3], [4], see [5] for a review).

The role of spatiotemporal congruency has been primarily studied in the multisensory integration literature [6], [7], [8], [9]. The general consensus is that spatial and temporal proximity of sensory cues is a crucial factor for whether and how cues should be integrated ([10], [11], [12], [13], [14] for reviews see [15] and [16]). The brain seems to assign sensory information from multiple senses to the same object or event if it falls within a close spatiotemporal window [17] (“assumption of sensory unity”, for a review see [18]). In other words, according to the unity assumption, the brain expects that sensory cues belonging to the same object should be proximal to each other in terms of space and time. However, this is not always the case. An everyday example for this would be integrating lightning and thunder. Current evidence suggests that the spatial and temporal congruency is more of a rule of thumb than a must have ([19], for a review see [20]). As per the

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unity assumption, the ideal spatiotemporal distance between the sensory cues for achieving the strongest binding is zero. However, simply watching a ventriloquist reveals that this spatiotemporal window is also flexible. Under controlled conditions, [21] suggests that for achieving ventriloquism, the timing difference between the auditory and visual information should be less than 150 ms and spatial distance should be within the audience's auditory discrimination threshold. Moreover, this flexible window seems not to be constant across modalities and tasks. Instead, the spatiotemporal window for sensory integration is variable. For instance, spatial congruency seems to be mostly important for spatial tasks [20].

In contrast to full multisensory integration, substitute or complimentary sensory information can be combined in a common map without integrating individual sensory information. Hence, combining sensory information for supplementing information from another sense does not require to assume that all sensory information have the same cause. Thus, sensory information could be combined in a more flexible spatiotemporal window than multisensory integration. For instance, visual search can be facilitated by an auditory cue that is spatially not aligned with the visual target (pip and pop effect, [22]). Nevertheless, it is plausible to assume a spatiotemporal window for arbitrating which sensory information should be combined. Like multisensory integration, this spatiotemporal window for combining multiple senses might depend on their modality and task requirements.

Similar to the binding problem that the brain faces each day, technologies utilizing multisensory signals have the challenging task of delivering multisensory signals that the brain can easily combine, integrate or segregate. These technologies often try to emulate real life by rendering virtual worlds with sensory information from multiple channels (e.g.,[23]). These environments are usually designed to be similar to the real world or to augment sensory experiences by substituting or supplementing sensory information. An important step for augmenting user experience and presence [24] through virtual applications is to create environments that feature congruent sensory information that substitutes or supplements an existing feature in the environment. For instance, visual information necessary for navigation can be substituted by auditory information to improve navigation in visually impaired populations [25], [26], [27]. Or, the surgical precision in teleoperated robot-assisted operations can be improved by supplementing force feedback information from the robot hand with a graphical representation [28].

A potential bottleneck for virtual reality applications is to generate multiple sensory signals through multiple devices in tandem [25]. Rendering multisensory signals is generally desirable as it improves virtual experience [29], [30]. Furthermore, the congruency of signals has been linked to better user presence [24] and less cyber sickness [31]. On the other hand, large spatiotemporal incongruencies can diminish user experience [32]. Despite the wide usage of multisensory environments and importance of spatiotemporal congruency, there is a knowledge gap about the spatial and temporal tolerances of delivering parallel stimulations for substituting or supplementing sensory experiences. This is an important question both for developing necessary technologies and for

understanding how a sensory signal is mapped onto a sensory dimension from another modality. Moreover, there is limited evidence on how flexible is the spatiotemporal window for cross dimensional mapping of rendered multisensory signals. Previous studies showed that both compliance [33] and stiffness [34] estimations in AR are modulated by delays in visual and haptic cues. Despite large delays up to 198 ms in visual feedback, participants still combined visual and tactile cues when estimating compliance. This is in line with another study showing that visuotactile simultaneity window in AR is about 195 ms [35]. Thus, for developing virtual devices that supplement sensory information, it is imperative to deliver sensory signals within a spatiotemporal window that is suitable for the modality and the task at hand.

Here, we investigated the flexibility of the spatiotemporal window for combining sensory information and how spatiotemporal discrepancies impact on sensory combination following virtual reality applications perspective. Given the spatiotemporal flexibility for cue combination we opted for extreme spatial and temporal discrepancies in order to characterize how cue combination is affected by spatial or temporal discrepancies. Considering the potential task and modality dependency of this window, we decided to use a task that exploits natural limitations of the visual system. Humans shift their gaze up to four times per second by executing saccadic eye movements. During the execution of these eye movements, visual sensitivity drops to a degree where it may not be possible to visually detect small changes in object positions. While saccades suppress the detection of displacements, other senses could supplement this imprecise visual information and improve detection. The saccadic suppression of displacement is a robust and a well-studied paradigm where a visual target is displaced to a near location during saccades [36], [37], [38], [39]. Here, we used a variant of this paradigm where participants were required to fixate instead of executing saccades to targets [40], [41], [42]. In this implementation, the visual masking that naturally occurs during saccades is simulated by a full screen noise that briefly masks the peripheral target before it is displaced. Like for saccadic suppression of displacement, the impairment caused by masking can be relieved when the masking period is followed by a blank screen before the visual target reappears at a new location [37], [40], [41], [43]. Here, we supplement visual displacement information with uncorrelated tactile displacement information to test the spatiotemporal flexibility in combining these cues.

In order to render visual and tactile displacement cues, we built a custom setup where visual and tactile displacement cues are generated by two independent devices. Our setup allows to manipulate visual and tactile cues independently from each other. Thus, it offers a simplified experimental platform to systematically produce different spatial and temporal congruencies that could burden more advanced display systems. Therefore, we were able to test whether imprecise visual displacement cues are substituted by uncorrelated but precise tactile displacement cues. More importantly, we checked if and how the spatial and temporal synchronicity of these cues is crucial for incorporating tactile cues into visual displacement judgments.

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II. METHODS

A. Participants

29 participants from Marburg University participated in the experiments. Six participants were excluded from statistical analyses as four participants failed to follow experiment instructions and two participants had points of subjective equalities (PSEs) outside of the measured range (see Data Analysis). Hence, the final sample included 23 participants (16 females, mean age = 24.74 ± 4.3). All participants had normal or corrected-to-normal (e.g., contact lenses) vision and did not report any tactile insensitivity on their right index finger where the tactile cues were administered. Participants signed written informed consent before the experiment and were compensated with 8 €/hour. The procedure was approved by the local ethics commission of the Department of Psychology (proposal number 2015-35k) and was in line with the Declaration of Helsinki (2013) except that the study was not preregistered.

B. Equipment and Setup

Fig. 1. Setup (a) and design (b) of the experiment. a) Participants reached to the braille cell that was located under the screen and corresponding to the visual target in the spatial congruency conditions. b) Example trials from visuotactile congruency conditions. None of the stimuli is drawn to scale. Braille cells are simplified in illustration as black boxes. Blue dots represent active pins for generating tactile displacements. Red arrows illustrate visual (4.5° , 3.25° , 2° , 1°) and tactile (0.33°) displacements in either direction.

The experiment was conducted with custom hardware consisting of a visual display and a braille device. The design of the setup was inspired from the hardware used to render conflicting multisensory information (e.g. [44], [45], [46], [47], [48]). The visual display was a DELL UltraSharp monitor (resolution: 2560×1440) that was fitted on a custom platform. With this platform, the screen height and angle were adjusted to allow participants to reach the braille device which was located on the back of the screen (Fig. 1a). The height and the angle of the display were fixed for all participants. With a chinrest and adjustable chair, we ensured that all participants

viewed the screen from a similar vantage point. The visual display was calibrated to provide linear luminance output (e.g., gamma correction). Following the calibration, the luminance for black, grey, and white pixels were 1.17, 126.53, and 259.74 cd/m^2 respectively.

Tactile displacement cues were generated by a commercial braille cell (b11: B11.cdr (metec-ag.de), Metec Ag.) designed for both private and research purposes. This device had successfully used in a similar design [49]. The braille cell has an array of 2×3 pins that can be individually manipulated on command. The diameter of each pin was 0.7 mm (Min tactile force = 17 cN, Dot stroke = 0.7 mm) and the distance between neighboring pins was 2.45 mm. The braille cell was placed behind the screen at an overlapping position with the visual stimulus except in the spatial incongruency condition. The tactile cue was generated by raising a single pin and switching it with a neighboring pin.

In all conditions, participant gaze position was recorded with an Eyelink 1000+ eye tracker (SR Research Ltd., ON, Canada) at 1000 Hz. At the beginning of all conditions, the eye tracker was calibrated using a 9-point calibration with 25° horizontal and 5° vertical steps from the screen center.

We used a custom MATLAB script to control both visual and tactile devices, record gaze position and participant responses. The visual stimulus was controlled using Psychtoolbox [50], [51]. Time stamps from the display were used to ensure proper timing of the visual stimuli and noise masks. To ensure fixation, gaze position was recorded in each trial through custom functions and the Eyelink toolbox extension of Psychtoolbox. The braille cell was controlled through MVBD which is a commercial software developed by the producer company. The onset and offset of the visual and tactile stimuli were controlled in MATLAB. To account for potential software and hardware delays, we also took initial measurements with a high-speed camera to ensure the temporal alignment of visual and tactile cues in different conditions.

C. Stimuli

In all trials there was a peripheral visual target located at 25° horizontal distance from the fixation on the same vertical axis. The visual stimulus was a dark gray square subtending an area of $0.53^\circ \times 0.53^\circ$ on a lighter gray background. To allow participants to distinguish the different conditions, the visual target was presented as a square in the visuotactile conditions and as a diamond in the visual only control condition. There was a brief full screen visual noise increasing the difficulty of judging visual displacements. The noise consisted of an equal number of dark and bright pixels that were randomly arranged for each trial. Thus, the mean luminance of the noise was equal to the background luminance.

In all conditions except in the visual only condition, there was also a tactile stimulus accompanying the visual target. The tactile stimulus was generated by raising one of the pins of the braille device that was located just under the visual stimulus from the participant's perspective. Thus, the size of the tactile stimulus was 0.7 mm or 0.1° . The tactile displacement was generated by retracting the raised pin and raising its neighboring pin at the same time. Thus, the size of tactile

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displacement was equal to the distance between two neighboring pins, which was 4.5 mm or 0.33° .

D. Procedure

Upon signing informed consents, participants were told that they will be helping to test a prototype of a new device capable of rendering objects with visual and tactile features. They were instructed to fixate on a fixation target and report the direction of the visual displacement (i.e., left or right) of the peripheral target. However, they received strict instruction that they should not totally ignore or rely on visual or tactile information alone. The experimenter did not mention or comment on the congruency of the visual and tactile cues in terms of direction or timing. However, at the beginning of the visual only block, the experimenter informed participants about the absence of tactile cues. Following the instructions, participants were seated comfortably in front of the visual display and placed their chin into the chinrest. Under the guidance of the experimenter, with their right arm, they reached to the back of the screen and placed their index finger on the braille cell.

All participants completed five separate blocks in one session. There were two control visual and three visuotactile conditions, completed in separate blocks. Hence, each block followed the same general trial structure in all conditions. At the beginning of each block, the experimenter ensured that participants were properly in contact with the braille cell by completing three test trials with the tactile cues without the visual target. Then, participants proceeded to the eye tracker calibration. Common to all conditions, each trial started with a fixation check, in which the participant had to press the space bar while fixating a fixation target located at the center of the display but randomly jittered 1° horizontally in each trial. Following a successful fixation check, the fixation target blinked to signal the start of the trial. After a random duration of 500-750 ms, the visual target appeared at a 25° horizontal distance from the fixation target. 300 ms after the visual target, a brief full screen noise occluded the visual target for 50 ms. Following the occlusion period, the visual target reappeared at a horizontally shifted location (4.5° , 3.25° , 2° , 1° either to the right or left) or at the same location. The visual target was displayed another 300 ms following the occlusion. Participants indicated the direction of the visual displacement with their left hand by pressing “F” or “J” on the keyboard for leftward and rightward displacement, respectively. In order to prevent, visual and postural fatigue participants were encouraged to take a short break at the end of each block.

The only difference between the two visual conditions was the spatial alignment of the visual target with respect to the braille cell. In the spatially congruent visual condition, the visual target appeared on top of the braille cell and the right index finger of the participants from their perspective. In the spatially incongruent condition, it appeared at the same horizontal distance to the screen center but on the opposite side of the braille cell. In both visual only conditions, the visual target either appeared immediately following the brief noise period or after a 300 ms blank period to relieve the effect of masking. During the blank period, only the fixation target was present on the screen.

In the visuotactile conditions, visual and tactile cues were spatially, temporally, or spatiotemporally aligned. The tactile displacement cues were generated by presenting a single pin for 300 ms then switching it with a neighboring pin that stayed raised for another 300 ms. Thus, the tactile displacement mimicked the visual displacement except, the size of tactile displacements was fixed. The direction of tactile displacements was the same as the visual displacement in half of the trials. Thus, the direction of the tactile displacement was uninformative about the visual displacement direction. In the spatial incongruency condition, the visual and tactile displacements occurred at opposite sides of the screen center. Therefore, in both visual and visuotactile spatial incongruency conditions, the visual stimuli located opposite to the participants index finger and the braille cell. In the temporal incongruency condition, the visual and tactile displacements were spatially aligned but the tactile displacement preceded the visual displacement by 200 ms.

Participants completed five blocks in random order. Each block contained 180 trials. In the visual only conditions, half of the trials had a 300 ms blank period which were not used in the current study. Therefore, the visual conditions tested with a single within-subjects factor of spatial congruency (Spatial Congruency: Aligned vs Misaligned). The visuotactile conditions followed a within-subjects design with one factor determining the spatial and temporal congruency (Congruency, Spatial incongruency, Temporal incongruency). The order of trials with and without blanking was random. The direction and the size of the visual displacements were fully randomized. The direction of the tactile displacement followed a random sequence which was fixed for all participants due to equipment restraints. Participants completed 900 trials, 180 trials per condition in around 100 minutes.

E. Data Analysis

Participants were instructed to fixate for the full duration of the trial until the response phase. We tracked their gaze location during this period. We discarded trials where the gaze location was detected outside of an imaginary square of $3^\circ \times 3^\circ$ around the fixation target. We identified and excluded four participants who regularly executed saccades to the visual target. For the remaining participants, we only excluded trials that violated our fixation criterion (5.42% of trials in all conditions). With the remaining data, we first fitted psychometric functions (cumulative gaussians) to the spatially congruent visual only condition which also served as a control condition for visual displacement judgments. The estimated PSEs of two participants were outside of the measured displacement range. Therefore, we excluded these participants as their psychometric functions were not viable for modelling.

We modeled the visual displacement judgments of participants in the visual only conditions by fitting individual psychometric functions separately for blanking and non-blanking conditions using Psignifit [52]. We estimated psychometric functions using normal cumulative gaussian functions with a beta prior of 5, 0 lapse rate and asymptote.

Visual displacement tasks with saccades reported to produce bias opposite to the saccade direction [43]. While our task did not involve saccades, participants were always in

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contact with the braille cell, which could serve as a reference for discerning visual displacement direction. This would result in participants having different visual biases or different thresholds for the visual information in spatial incongruency and the other visuotactile conditions would be different. As a control for any difference in discrimination thresholds and directional bias in visual judgments, we first compared the spatially congruent and incongruent visual only conditions (see *Supplementary Materials*). We did not find any evidence suggesting a difference in discrimination threshold or bias in non-blanking trials between the two conditions. Hence, we used the spatially aligned visual only condition for estimating the perceptual performance in all visuotactile conditions.

For the visuotactile conditions, we observed large biases in the direction of tactile displacement. For some participants, these biases did not allow to estimate a psychometric function for the measured visual displacements. Thus, we estimated the perceptual performance in these conditions using the tactile and visual displacement cues, detailed in the *Modelling* section.

Analysis and modelling were done with custom scripts in MATLAB 2022a (Math Works Inc.).

F. Modeling

Fig 2. Data and model for one participant. First, the visual estimates were derived by fitting a psychometric function to the visual only condition (solid line). Then the tactile estimations for leftward tactile displacements (green line) and combination weights (W_v) were fitted to obtain a model for visuotactile displacements (gray line) with least-squared errors. Blue dots show the observed data in visual only and visuotactile conditions with leftward tactile displacements.

We modelled participant judgments in the visuotactile conditions with a model that is more parsimonious than other, more popular models in multisensory integration literature such as maximum likelihood estimation (MLE, [53], [54]) and causal inference [11], [12]. Our model linearly combined the visual and tactile displacement estimates in the form of weighted summation (Fig. 2). We based on our modeling approach on the hypothesis that spatial and temporal discrepancies will

modulate how visual and tactile information are combined. Thus, we expected that participants would weigh visual and tactile information differently across conditions according to the reliability of visual and tactile information [48].

To this end, we modelled the perceptual judgments in different congruency conditions by linearly combining the visual and tactile displacement estimates. We obtained the visual displacement estimates (E_V) for each participant by fitting individual psychometric functions to their performance in the visual only condition. We obtained tactile estimates (E_T) also with cumulative gaussian functions. As we did not observe any directional bias in the piloting stage and given the fact that the size of displacements in both directions was equal, we estimated the tactile judgments with a mean of zero (i.e., assuming no direction bias) and used a free parameter for determining the width of the cumulative gaussians (i.e., just-noticeable-difference). Then, we used the visual and tactile estimates to separately model the congruency conditions. For each condition (E_{VT}), we linearly combined these estimates with a free weighting parameter. Therefore, each congruency condition was modelled by combining the same visual and tactile estimates with a different weighting parameter.

III. RESULTS

From the visuotactile combination models we extracted weights of visual and tactile information in each condition, to check how the combination of visual and tactile cues is modulated by large spatial or temporal discrepancies.

Fig. 3. Modelled tactile weights for congruency and temporal incongruency conditions. Mean haptic weights for the temporal incongruency and congruency conditions are presented with error bars showing 95% confidence interval for congruency (horizontal), temporal incongruency (vertical) conditions.

Figure 3 shows the relationship between the influence of tactile information in the temporal incongruency and the congruency conditions. We found that the influence of tactile information was correlated in the congruency condition and the

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temporal incongruency condition ($\rho(22) = 0.84, p < 0.001$). In other words, there was a linear relationship in how participants weighted the tactile information when it was spatiotemporally aligned or when it preceded the visual targets

Fig. 4. Modelled tactile weights for congruency and spatial incongruency conditions. Mean haptic weights for the spatial incongruency and congruency conditions are presented with error bars showing 95% confidence interval for congruency (horizontal), spatial incongruency (vertical) conditions.

by 200 ms. In addition, they tended to use more tactile information under temporal discrepancy compared to congruency condition. In order to test whether temporal incongruency significantly changed the weighting of tactile information, we first standardized the changes in tactile weights across visuotactile conditions by applying a Z transformation to tactile weights of each participant. A Wilcoxon signed rank on the z-transformed data yielded a significant difference in tactile weights ($z = 2.128, p = 0.033$), suggesting an increase in tactile weighting with temporal incongruency. Thus, under temporal discrepancy participants simply increased their use of tactile information without altering their overall weighting pattern.

We followed the same approach and compared the tactile weightings in the spatial incongruency condition to spatiotemporal condition (Fig. 4). In contrast to temporal incongruency condition, participants seemed to adjust their weighting of tactile information independently from the tactile weights in the congruency condition. More specifically, while for some participants the weighting of tactile information was increased with spatial discrepancy, for others it decreased hinting at individual differences on how participants used the spatially discrepant tactile information. In line with this, there was no correlation between tactile weights in spatial incongruency and spatiotemporal congruency conditions ($\rho(22) = 0.35, p = 0.103$). This relationship was also significantly weaker than the relationship between the temporal incongruency and congruency conditions as indicated by the Fisher r to z transformed data (Fisher $z = 2.706, p = 0.003$). In contrast to the temporal incongruency condition, we did not

observe an increase in tactile weights compared to congruency condition ($z = 1.025, p = 0.301$). Interestingly, unlike temporal incongruency, the spatial discrepancy seemed to modulate tactile weights differently for different observers.

To further analyze these inter-participant differences, we calculated the change in tactile weights in incongruency conditions relative to the congruency condition (Fig. 5). There was no correlation between the relative change in tactile weights in spatial and temporal incongruency conditions

Fig. 5. Tactile weights in the incongruency conditions relative to the congruency condition. Error bars show 95% confidence interval for temporally incongruent (horizontal) and spatially incongruent (vertical) visual conditions.

($r(22) = -0.028, p = 0.9$). We observed that the tactile weights in spatial and temporal incongruency conditions were shifted towards opposite directions for 9 out of 23 participants (Shaded area in Fig. 5). We tested if these participants form a distinctly separate group by comparing the frequency of participants showing different weighting patterns (the four quadrants in Fig 5) using an exact McNemar test. However, there was no significant difference between the frequency of participants showing different patterns of combination ($\chi^2 = 1.923, p = 0.166$).

IV. DISCUSSION

We found that tactile displacement cues can be combined with visual displacement cues and influence visual displacement judgments. We modelled the influence of the tactile cues using a linear model that combines estimation for visual and tactile unisensory estimates. Our results suggest that the weighting of unisensory estimates in cue combination are prone to change in the face of large spatiotemporal discrepancy between the underlying unisensory estimates. This is in line with previous research on multisensory integration suggesting that the strength of multisensory integration, how likely is to perceive two signals to be belonging to the same source, is dependent on the degree of spatial and temporal alignment of the multisensory signals. in general [6]. We observed that

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spatial and temporal discrepancies impact differently the weighting of individual cues.

The temporal discrepancy increased the weighting of tactile information but was still correlated with the congruent condition. This is in line with a previous AR study showing that visuotactile compliance estimations are modulated by temporal discrepancy [34]. Together with our results, we argue that temporal proximity of visual and tactile cues determines how they will be combined. This change in combination weights is to be expected as both adults and infants can use temporal discrepancy to segregate different cues [55]. This is also in line with previous studies emphasizing the role of temporal congruency in multisensory integration [8], [10], [14], [56]. However, it is important to note that the majority of evidence for the importance of temporal alignment stems from studies using auditory and visual cues [14], [21], [56]. These studies suggest an integration window of 200 ms for audiovisual stimuli [21] as opposed to visuoproprioceptive cues with a window of 400 ms [57]. In agreement with this, temporal discrepancies can shape how visuoproprioceptive cues are combined [46], [58]. Particularly, perceptual biases introduced by multisensory binding as in the rubber hand illusion weaken with increasing temporal discrepancy between the unisensory cues [46]. Crucially, the window of integration and perhaps combination is not contingent on the physical simultaneity but when the simultaneity of arrival of the two signals to the brain [59]. Moreover, different neural mechanisms are responsible for binding asynchronous audiotactile cues within different time windows [60]. In addition to differences in the temporal integration windows of different pairs of modalities, integration windows can depend on stimulus features within a modality. For instance, the temporal window for combining audiovisual signals shrinks with increasing signal intensities [61]. Similarly, different stimulus types and where and how they are applied could modulate the window of combination. Our results, suggest that 200 ms delay between the tactile and visual displacement cues altered how they are combined. In our study, for generating tactile displacements we used mechanical cutaneous stimulations to the right index finger. Thus, we would expect that our findings can be generalized across different body sites. However, this temporal window might vary for other cutaneous stimulations such as thermal or kinesthetic stimuli. Thus, the efficiency of sensory augmentation systems might depend on the temporal sensitivity of different neural mechanisms that combine cues from various modalities.

Previous studies provided mixed evidence on the role of spatial congruency on how visual and tactile or proprioceptive cues are combined. For instance, tactile elevation judgments can be biased by visual cues at different locations. However, the strength of this bias decreases as a function of the distance between the tactile and visual cues [62]. Relatedly, the combination of multiple synchronous visual cues with the same proprioceptive cue is weighted depending on the distance between the individual visual cues and the proprioceptive cues [58]. Yet, in some occasions, the binding of visual and tactile cues can still occur under very large spatial discrepancies at a comparable strength to binding of the same cues without spatial discrepancy [63]. In our experiment while temporal congruency

has systematically shifted the tactile weights, we found that spatial discrepancy yielded a less systematic outcome. We observed that in the face of spatial incongruency, tactile weights changed independently from the congruent condition. Interestingly, tactile weights for almost half of the participants drastically changed compared to the congruency and temporal incongruency conditions. The spatial incongruency altered the combination weights for these participants to a degree that the weights for tactile and visual information switched places. This is reminiscent of a phenomenon called cue switching, where individual unisensory cues are alternately used for estimating multisensory signals [8]. The altering combination weights could also be attributed to attentional deployment. Previous studies have shown that spatially separated cues from different sensory channels attracts attention towards themselves even when they are task irrelevant ([3], [4], see [5] for a review). As both visual and tactile cues were task relevant, participants might have been forced to choose which cue to attend or to switch between them. This interparticipant variation could have also hindered any change in tactile weights as a result of spatial incongruency.

We further inspected the apparent individual differences caused by spatial incongruency by comparing relative weight changes in temporal and spatial incongruency conditions. We did not find significantly distinct groups. However, we had a relatively small sample for testing individual differences. Furthermore, our participants were mostly young adults, so that our results may not reflect how other age groups might be affected by spatiotemporal discrepancies as multisensory processing abilities decrease at later ages [64]. Similarly, participants with different degree of familiarity with multisensory platforms or technology usage might differ in their sensitivity to spatiotemporal discrepancies. For instance, video game players might combine multisensory information differently as they have enhanced spatiotemporal sensitivity than non-gamers [65], [66]. Thus, the spatiotemporal window for cue combination might be smaller for professionals using these technologies or frequent video gamers who are experienced with using proximal cues. Therefore, difference in experience with gaming or virtual experience across our participants might explain the different combination strategies that we observed. Similarly, differences may exist in clinical populations as individuals with autism spectrum disorder (ASD) are less affected from the brightness-weight illusion when judging the weight of visuotactile objects [67]. More importantly, the spatiotemporal window for combining multisensory signals could be different or more variable for patient groups, such as autism spectrum disorder [68] or schizophrenia [69]. Finally, the spatiotemporal window might change over the course of treatment for patients recovering from physical injuries. Hence, we encourage prospective studies to check these differences which can stem from various experienced-based, innate or developmental factors.

Investigating individual differences in cue combination could have direct implications for applications such as augmented reality. Identifying individual differences in the spatiotemporal window of combining sensory information is crucial for the effectiveness and user experience of technologies rendering multisensory information. This is especially

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imperative for platforms with wide range of users and applications. For instance, determining an adequate spatiotemporal window might be critical for feelings of realism, or even presence with respect to visuotactile rendering technologies. These technologies can be used to render 3D visuotactile virtual objects [70], or to render tactile cues supplementing visual information in online shopping [71]. Considering that the spatiotemporal proximity of the visual and tactile signals can influence how they are combined by different users, our results can potentially contribute to the development of rendering realistic visuotactile objects. Additionally, our results can contribute to prosthetics and artificial skin development that aims to create a seamless integration to one's body with similar spatiotemporal sensitivity (e.g. [72]). As these health technologies target a wide user range differing in many aspects approximating the spatiotemporal sensitivity of individuals could improve their integration. Furthermore, virtual reality is commonly used for entertainment among gamers but also used for therapy and patient care. These populations might have different spatiotemporal tolerances and therefore, applications targeting these populations might need to use different spatiotemporal tolerances for successful implementation. Further individualized calibration might be necessary for high precision tasks as spatial congruency improves task execution [60]. For instance, in teleoperations, operators benefit from visually supplementing the force information from the robotic arms [28]. The precision of the operator in these dynamic and demanding procedures might benefit from sensory substitution systems calibrated for the operator. Considering the wide range of individual variables and precision demands, future applications could benefit from identifying the individual spatiotemporal window of their users for achieving the best interaction.

In the current study, we tested the impact of spatial and temporal discrepancies within controlled but simplified laboratory conditions. Using our setup, we systematically reproduced spatiotemporal incongruencies that might be present in more advanced systems. We showed that spatiotemporal incongruencies could alter how sensory cues are combined at least for simple environments. Future studies could verify the impact of spatiotemporal incongruencies in AR/VR with more complex environments and tasks. While the richness of the rendered environment boosts its realism and sensory integration [74], it could lead to a tidier spatiotemporal window as multiple cues would be competing for integration and combination [75]. Therefore, future studies could address how scene complexity, or the number of competing cues modulate the spatiotemporal window for combining cues from different objects and senses.

The rapid advance in technology makes it possible to render realistic experiences for a wide range of applications including gaming and digital therapies. These applications augment sensory experience by supplementing proximal cues that provide information that otherwise wouldn't be available to users. In this study, we found that the spatiotemporal congruency of visual and tactile cues to be a crucial factor for combining visual and tactile information for making visual displacement judgments. We argue that temporally discrepancy tips the combination weights towards one source of sensory

estimate. In contrast, our results hint at potential individual differences in how individuals combine spatially discrepant sensory information. Thus, we recommend that multisensory applications assess individual spatiotemporal limits for combining sensory cues for improving task performance and user satisfaction for various subpopulations.

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SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIALS

Participants performed two visual conditions. In the spatially aligned conditions, the visual target appeared directly above their right index finger whereas in the other condition it was at a mirrored location. When the index finger is aligned with the visual target, it can serve as a landmark and improve visual displacement judgments even in the absence of any tactile displacement cues. To test this possibility, we compared the just noticeable differences (JNDs) in the visual only conditions without blanking when the index finger was at the same or the mirror location of the visual target (Supplementary Fig. 1). A paired sample t-test yielded no significant differences ($t(22) = 0.577, p = 0.567$) indicating that there was no significant improvement due to location of the visual stimulus relative to the finger.

Supplementary Fig. 1. PSEs and JNDs in the visual only conditions without blanking. Mean JND and PSE presented with error bars showing 95% confidence interval for spatially congruent (horizontal), spatially incongruent (vertical) visual conditions and their comparison (diagonal).

Visual displacement tasks with saccades reported to produce bias opposite to the saccade direction [43]. In both conditions, there was a slight bias to report more inward displacements (towards fixation) than outward displacement. However, there was no difference in bias between the two conditions ($t(22) = 1.175, p = 0.253$). Since there were no differences in JNDs and PSEs between the non-blanking spatially congruent and incongruent conditions, we used the trials from the spatially congruent visual only condition to separately model the visuotactile conditions. Our model allows us to measure the weighting of visual and tactile information in our participants' visual displacement judgment separately in spatiotemporal, spatial, and temporal congruency conditions.